

Studies on Synthesis and Anthelmintic Activity of N-(Substituted Phenoxy Acetamido) Phthalimides

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A series of N-(substituted phenoxy acetamido)phthalimides (1-21) have been synthesised and screened for their cestodicidal activity against *Hymenolepis nana* infection in rats. The compound 14 was found to be the most active compound of the series showing 50.6% clearance of infection at a dose of 250 mg/kg given for 3 days.

PHTHALIC acid derivatives have been recently reported to possess marked anthelmintic activity¹. The broad spectrum of biological activity has been associated with phenoxy acetic acid nucleus². Hence, it was thought that the molecules containing both the moieties would have a more pronounced biological activity. The present paper describes the synthesis and anthelmintic activity of N-(substituted phenoxy acetamido)phthalimide (1-21).

Reactions of substituted phenols with ethyl chloro acetate and hydrazine hydrate yielded substituted phenoxy acetyl hydrazines³. Condensation of phenoxy acetyl hydrazines with substituted phthalic anhydride gave N-(substituted phenoxy acetamido)-phthalimides (1-21).

Experimental

The structure of all the compounds were checked by ir (KBr) recorded on Perkin-Elmer 157 and 177 infracord spectrophotometers. NMR spectra were recorded on Varian A60-D and Perkin-Elmer R₃₂ spectrophotometers using TMS as internal reference. The chemical shifts are given in δ values. The mass spectra of the compounds were taken on JEOL-JMS-D300 instrument. Melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected.

Synthesis of substituted phenoxy acetyl hydrazines : The substituted phenoxy acetyl hydrazines were prepared according to the method of Conti³.

Synthesis of N-(4-nitrophenoxy acetamido)phthalimide (1) : A mixture of *p*-nitrophenoxy acetyl hydrazine (2.1 g ; 0.01 mole) and phthalic anhydride (1.48 g ; 0.01 mole) was heated on a free flame for 15 min. A jelly like mass separated out on cooling, which was washed with water. The solid thus separated was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 178°, yield, 2.0 g (60%). IR ν max (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3300 (NH), 2900 (CH_2), 1680 (C=O), 1520, 1340 (NO_2), 1245 (C-O-C). NMR (CDCl_3) : 8.0-8.5 (br, l, NH), 6.7-7.34 (m, 4, Ar-H), 7.5-7.9 (m, 4, phthalimide-Ar-H), 3.83 (s, 2, CH_2). Mass : M^+ at m/z : 341. Analysis : Found : C, 56.00 ; H, 2.94 ; N, 12.12. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$; C, 56.30 ; H, 3.22 ; N, 12.31%.

Other N-(substituted phenoxy acetamido)phthalimides (2-21) were prepared in a similar manner and the results are given in Table 1.

Biological activity : All the compounds were tested *in vivo* for their cestodicidal activity against *Hymenolepis nana* infection in rats by the technique of Steward⁴. The compounds were administered orally at dosages 500, 400 and 250 mg/kg using three rats per experimental group. Yomesan was used as the standard drug in all control experiments and it cleared 100% of the above infection at a single oral dose of 50 mg/kg. The results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	Yield* %	Cestodicidal activity against <i>H. nana</i>	
					Dose mg/kg	% efficiency
R=H						
1.	4-NO ₂	H	178	60	250	12.2
2.	3-OCH ₃	5-OCH ₃	162	55	500	Inactive
3.	4-CH ₃	H	164	64	400	10.0
4.	2-CH ₃	H	110	60	250	15.4
5.	4-Cl	3-CH ₃	204	70	250	20.0
6.	4-C ₆ H ₅	H	210	60	500	Inactive
7.	3-CH ₃	H	112	60	400	13.2
8.	2-CHO	H	262	65	400	18.0
9.	2-Cl	H	148	70	250	22.4
10.	4-Cl	H	168	62	250	25.0
11.	H	H	120	67	250	28.0
R=NO ₂						
12.	4-C ₆ H ₅	H	172	50	250	25.0
13.	4-Cl	3-OH ₃	160	66	250	49.2
14.	4-NO ₂	H	208	63	250	50.6
15.	4-CH ₃	H	198	62	250	30.0
16.	3-OH ₃	H	260	65	250	25.0
17.	2-Cl	H	184	59	250	45.8
18.	2-CHO	H	238	70	250	35.2
19.	2-CH ₃	H	134	60	400	15.0
20.	H	H	154	60	250	28.0
21.	4-Cl	H	198	55	250	48.0

* All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses and were within $\pm 0.5\%$ of the theoretical values.

Results and Discussion

The cestodicidal activity exhibited by N-(substituted phenoxy acetamido)phthalimides against *H. nana* infection in rats is shown in Table 1. The compound 14 at a dose of 250 mg/kg given for 3 days caused 50.6% removal of *H. nana* in rats. The rest of the compounds were found inactive or showed insignificant activity at doses of 500, 400 or 250 mg/kg.

Based on the cestodicidal activity data (Table 1), the following minimal structural parameters may be defined for optimal activity.

(i) Introduction of electron withdrawing group at R₁ and R₂ positions enhanced the cestodicidal activity whereas electron donating group reduced the activity.

(ii) Presence of pharmacophores with electron withdrawing ability (e.g., NO₂) in phthalimide ring

(12-21) is an important factor governing the cestodicidal activity.

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